

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZATION OF MILITARY EQUIPMENT MAINTENANCE BASED ON COMBAT EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

The article is prepared on the topical issues related to maintaining the technical condition (TC) of military equipment (ME) at the proper level in the course of combat operations (CO), by conducting maintenance. The article examines the organization of maintenance of ME on the basis of experience in combat operations.

Keywords: combat operations; military equipment; technical condition; maintenance.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Experience of combat operations in the Anti-Terrorist Operation area, later during the Joint Forces Operation (JFO) [1], as well as amid a full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation troops, showed that the existing approaches as for the organization of the maintenance system in the Armed Forces of Ukraine (AFU) are outdated both in the conditions of hybrid warfare and applying of modern means of destruction by the enemy [1-2].

If we conditionally divide the course of combat operations (CO) in the east of Ukraine into three main stages, the first one can be characterized by the active phase of combat operations with significant movements of ME, considerable use of motor resources of ME, as well as heavy load on maintenance elements. [1]. The first stage lasted during 2014. The second stage might be characterized as a "positional war", when the opposing sides almost do not change their positions, while the resource of equipment is spent, though with less intensity than during the first stage, but still quite significantly. The duration of this period can be outlined from 2015 after the stabilization of the contact line until February 24, 2022. The third stage began with the full-scale invasion of the territory of Ukraine by the Russian Fed-

eration troops and their accomplices, and is again characterized by significant consumption of motor resources of equipment and heavy load on technical elements.

In addition, the adoption of the latest modern samples of western weapons by the Armed Forces of Ukraine requires additional training of personnel in familiarization with the structure and maintenance of ME, significantly diversifies their list and, as a result, the burden on maintenance elements to search for unique spare parts increases.

Formulation of the problem. Due to the beginning of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation troops, and modernization of the Armed Forces of Ukraine with new samples of western weapons [3-4], a contradiction arises between the requirements of the main provisions of the existing maintenance system and the current state in the conditions of CO.

Analysis of recent research and publications. When searching for scientific publications in this subject area, one can not ignore the scientific works of well-known scientists, such as V. Birkov [5], O. Vorobiov [6], V. Sivak [7], and other researchers, who have quite deeply revealed the approaches to the management of technical condition (TC) of ME.

The purpose of the article. To develop recommendations on the maintenance system structure of ME on the basis of the analysis of experience in carrying out maintenance of ME activities during the previous stages of CO.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

There is a planned preventive maintenance system for ME in the Armed Forces of Ukraine, the essence of which is that all types of maintenance are carried out according to the plan after the ME has worked out the established period or operating time, regardless of its current TC, in order to prevent possible malfunctions and failures, and current repairs are carried out as needed (depending on the TC of ME).

It should be noted that such a system of maintenance has remained virtually unchanged in the Armed Forces of Ukraine since the Soviet Union, and attempts to switch to modern progressive systems rested on the need to update the fleet of ME, that has also remained unchanged since then.

This system assumed the obligatory conduct of the following types of ME maintenance in daily use:

- control inspection (CI);
- daily maintenance (DM);
- maintenance No. 1 (M-1);
- maintenance No. 2 (M-2);
- seasonal service (SS) [2, 4].

The purpose of CI is to check and ensure traffic safety and faultless operation of ME while performing the assigned task. It is conducted by a driver (driver mechanic) under the control of unit commanders.

Particular attention during the inspection before leaving the park is paid to the serviceability of the steering, braking system, lighting and signaling equipment, serviceability of chassis, refueling with operating materials, fastening of equipment and cargo.

During CI on the road attention is paid to the absence of leakage of operating materials, their level in the engine cooling and lubrication systems, the degree of heating of transmission units and assemblies, chassis, working equipment, the condition of the chassis units.

Daily maintenance is one of the main types of maintenance. It is carried out every day after the end of ME operation in order to prepare it for further use.

The following works are performed: refueling with operating materials; cleaning, washing; checkup of the technical condition of assemblies, mechanisms, systems and operational equipment; elimination of detected malfunctions during operation; checking the completeness, condition and stowage of an individual set of spare parts, entrenching tools and other organic property.

Numbered maintenance №1 and №2 are intended to check ME, identify and eliminate malfunctions, ensure reliable operation until the next numbered maintenance [2, 4].

M-1 includes works performed during DM, technical diagnostics of ME and a number of additional fastening, lubrication, control and adjustment works, as well as elimination of detected malfunctions.

M-2 includes work performed during M-1 and a number of additional fastening, lubrication, control and adjustment works that provide maintenance of all systems, units and assemblies.

SS is carried out 2 times a year in order to ensure trouble-free operation of ME in the future autumn-winter or spring-summer period of operation. During SS the regular numbered maintenance and additional works on preparation of vehicles for the corresponding season are performed.

However, after the beginning of active COs on the territory of Ukraine, this system was adjusted in a certain way. This was due to the specifics of the COs, which most of the time had the form of "positional warfare".

Thus, the units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, together with their ME, for quite a long time were involved in the conduct of COs on more or less stable positions, and after the rotation were taken to "rest" to permanent deployment points (PDP) or to areas of combat capability restoration, where personnel were given vacations, equipment maintenance was performed, replenishment of units and training of personnel were carried out. After that, the brigades were again deployed to the combat areas, where they replaced other units [1-2].

In the course of the analysis of the maintenance activities organization during the first and second stages of the war in eastern Ukraine certain peculiarities of their conduct were formulated, which are also valid for the third stage, taking into account the echelon of ME deployment:

units that are in direct contact with the enemy must maintain ME in constant readiness for combat use, so they are able to carry out maintenance activities in an amount that does not exceed DM;

the units in the second echelon have the opportunity to carry out DM activities and the most necessary maintenance activities from the list of M-1;

numbered maintenance activities can be carried out only under the condition that units and subunits are withdrawn to the PDP or to the areas of combat capability restoration if there is time, appropriate forces and means.

Meanwhile, the list of measures during conduct of DM of ME that is in direct contact with the enemy, primarily includes carrying out the activities on replenishment of ammunition, refueling with operational materials to its normal amount and restoring order inside the vehicle.

At the same time, it is strictly forbidden to unload ammunition and carry out activities that lead to even a temporary suspension of the combat readiness of ME sample. The only exception may be the case when SS of ME is carried out, during which it is allowed to operate the ME with unloading of its ammunition, but not more than 30% of the total amount of available ME and with mandatory cover by other means.

As for the samples of foreign-made ME, it is necessary to try to carry out all the primary and mandatory measures, provided by the regulatory and technical documentation during DM, if ME is in the first echelon.

The rest of the measures, by analogy with domestic weapons, should be carried out in the areas of combat capability restoration or PPD.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

Thus, if to analyze the frequency of involvement of the Armed Forces of Ukraine units in carrying out of combat missions, we can conclude that most of the time

ME of the units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine perform combat missions, so maintenance activities are mainly carried out in the scope of DM, in some cases, M-1. And only for a short period of time, when units are withdrawn, it is possible to carry out certain labor-intensive types of maintenance.

Such state of affairs makes it necessary to consider the possibility of introducing a single annual maintenance as a key measure to maintain ME, which will be carried out when units are withdrawn and contain a list of basic mandatory measures to maintain the vehicle fleet.

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ПУТИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ СТРОИТЕЛЬНЫХ НОРМ И ПРАВИЛ «УСТАНОВКИ СОЛНЕЧНОГО ГОРЯЧЕГО ВОДОСНАБЖЕНИЯ» РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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WAYS OF IMPROVEMENT OF BUILDING REGULATIONS AND RULES OF "INSTALLATIONS OF SOLAR HOT WATER SUPPLY" REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Аннотация

Рассмотрены вопросы дальнейшего совершенствования строительных норм и правил “Установки солнечного горячего водоснабжения”, действующих на территории Республики Узбекистан, с целью широкомасштабного внедрения инновационных решений и новых технологий для повышения энергоэффективности проектируемых гелиоустановок.

Цель работы – определение основных путей для дальнейшей переработки республиканского нормативного документа, отвечающего современным требованиям и обеспечивающего повышение энергоэффективности проектируемых установок солнечного горячего водоснабжения на 30 %, а также улучшающих их эксплуатационные характеристики и надёжность работы в климатических условиях Узбекистана.

Выполнен анализ общепризнанных результатов законченных научно-исследовательских, опытно-конструкторских и экспериментальных работ в области систем солнечного горячего водоснабжения. Изучен и обобщен отечественный и зарубежный опыт проектирования, строительства и эксплуатации установок солнечного горячего водоснабжения различного назначения. Осуществлён отбор передовых технических достижений и научных исследований разных стран в области энергосбережения и эффективного использования солнечной энергии. В процессе дальнейшей переработки нормативного документа рекомендуется исключить устаревшие положения, а также включить новые нормативные требования, учитывающие современный уровень научно-технических достижений, проектно-строительной практики и региональные особенности Республики Узбекистан.